

Research

SWOT analysis at PT Grand Textile Industry in Indonesia

Rakotoarisoa Zamelina Arnold ^{1*}

¹ Strategic Management in Master Management Program, Parahyangan Catholic University, Indonesia

**Corresponding author*

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Abstract: One of the keys for proficiency in a company is the implementation of a good and efficient strategy management. This study is especially focus on the use of SWOT analysis in a local company in Indonesia, the PT GRAND TEXTILE INDUSTRY. This method is used to do both analysis of internal and external environment which is shown by the result presented on the table 2. PT GRAND TEXTILE is one among the top company in Indonesia. However, some issues within its organization and also related to its supplier are noted. Hence, capture and entering in a new market as international market is challenging. But still it could increase the rate of its market share. In order to bring help, SWOT analysis is proposed in this study. Therefore, the result will be analyzed, see and explain the meaning of strategic management of the company, compare its position and discuss about the result to give some adjustments and appropriate recommendations. From this study, six strategies are deducted from SWOT matrix including the strategy that will be proposed to the company to improve its production rate, its process performance rate, and its cost of the raw material.

Keywords: analysis, SWOT matrix, strategy, recommendation.

I- Introduction

Nowadays, textile is one of competitive field in this era of industry. Indonesia is ranked among the top ten largest textile producing countries. The textile and garment industry are one of Indonesia's oldest industries and being labor intensive a large source for jobs. However, the nation is far away from threatening China's dominant position. Whereas China controls about 35 percent of global textile markets, Indonesia controls only about 2 percent. Textile and Its Products industry (abbreviated as TPT) plays an important role in the Indonesia's employment and non-oil export. The most recent data shows that there have been not less than 2,869 companies involved in the

TPT industry, which can absorb and create employment as much as 1.4 million workers or 11% of the total workforce in the entire manufacturing industry. The TPT industry is also able to create export commodities valuing at US\$12.9 billion in the year 2017. The export performance of the TPT industry reaches up to 9% of Indonesia's total non-oil and gas exports. It is not surprising that this industry is considered as one of leading Indonesian non-oil exports and employment creation. TPT companies in Indonesia contributed to a total investment of Rp150.5 trillion. This figure slightly increases compared to 2,853 companies and total investment Rp. 146.1 trillion in the previous year. (Source from: <https://bisnis.tempo.co/read/1126749/mendag-pertumbuhan-industri-tekstil-indonesia-luar-biasa>).

The main objective of this research is to analyze the internal and external factors problem which can influence the decreasing of production within the company; to explore all different strategies that the company can use; and to be able to propose the appropriate strategies to the company.

II- Literature review

2.1. Strategy and types of strategies

Strategy is the creation of a unique position in carrying out a set of activities that require making tradeoffs in competing to choose what not to do, and involves in creating fit among these activities (Porter, 1996, November–December). Business strategy builds the roadmap to accomplish strategic goal achievement driven by competition, own capabilities, or innovation (Giannoulis & Zdravkovic, n.d.). Few companies have a clear strategic vision (Kim & Mauborgne, 2000). Neilson, Martin, & Powers (2008, June) showed in their research that organization fails to execute strategy as they straightly go to the structural reorganization and become indifferent in most powerful drivers for effectiveness like instead clarifying right decision and ensuring information flows where it is needed.

According to Fred R. David, Forest R. David, in *Strategic Management concepts and cases*, a competitive advantage approach, 16th edition. The model illustrated in the following figure provides a conceptual basis for applying strategic management. Defined and exemplified in Table below, alternative strategies that an enterprise could pursue can be categorized into 11 actions: forward integration, backward integration, horizontal integration, market penetration, market development, product development, related diversification, unrelated diversification, retrenchment, divestiture, and liquidation. Each alternative strategy has countless variations.

Table 1: Alternative strategies defined

STRATEGY	DEFINITION
Forward integration	Gaining ownership or increased control over distributors or retailers
Backward integration	Seeking ownership or increased control of a firm's suppliers
Horizontal integration	Seeking ownership of or increased control over a firm's competitors
Market penetration	Seeking to increase market share for present products or services in present markets through greater marketing efforts
Market development	Introducing present products or services into new geographic areas
Product development	Seeking increased sales by improving or modifying present products or services
Related diversification	Adding new but related products or services
Unrelated diversification	Adding new but unrelated products or services
Retrenchment	Regrouping through cost and asset reduction to reverse declining sales and profits
Divestiture	Selling a division or part of an organization
Liquidation	Selling all of a company's assets, in parts, for their tangible worth

Source: Fred R. David, Strategic management, "alternative strategies defined and exemplified", Part 2 Strategy formulation, chapter 5 Strategies in action, pages 130.

2.2. Environmental analysis

This analysis consists of some activities such as monitoring, evaluating, and collecting information from external and internal environment from a company.

2.2.1. External Environment Analysis

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This analysis is measurement that is useful for observer (external marketing environment) macro-factor environment that impacts organization. It observes politic, economy, social, technology, environment, and law aspect of an organization. This tool is needed to measure the growth of market, market position and business development.

1. Politic Factor

Including tax rate, international trade rules, political stability, labor law, environment law, and etc. Organization needs to keep their marketing balance by controlling it with the regulations existed.

2. Economy Factor

Economy factor includes economy growth, inflation, currency, and etc. It can be both macro and micro economy.

3. Social Factor

Social factor considers attributes like demographic population, revenue distribution, lifestyle, social mobility, recreation and shopping behavior, and etc. These factors directly influence the product. Social analysis helps understand the customer's view and what forces them to do so.

4. Technology Factor

Technology factor can omit obstacles to enter the market. This helps to bring new innovation such as automatic business process, for instance, people can find innovative ways to produce in order to get economic scale and reduce time cycle which affects cost and performance. On the other hand, technology can facilitate every similar information.

5. Law Factor

Law factor is included to company law, labor law, remuneration law, consumer rights, and other laws. This is really important that a company needs to understand what they have to do and what they do not have to do for trading success. If a global trade organization, then this is a significant area to take care because every country has its own regulations.

6. Environment Factor

Environment factor has been a challenging issue because a lot of obstacles and scarcity. Factors

that are included here are carbon emission, weather, habit, sickness, raw materials, pollution, and etc.

In general, a company needs to carefully understand the macro economy or demographic economy. Technology, law politic, culture, and main internal environment (customers, competitors, distribution, and suppliers) that influence the ability to get profit. The company must have good marketing to get to know the state-of-the-art technology happening. Management needs to identify opportunity and threat happened.

Opportunities is a favorable situations and factors can strengthen competitive advantage of the business or provide the business with new sources of competitive advantage. The list of major opportunities for a business may include new product development, finding new customer segment for existing products and opportunities for further cost reductions.

Threats is an unfavorable situations and factors could create problems for the business, compromising its competitive advantage to a certain extent. The most noteworthy threats faced by businesses include, but not limited to the loss of key members of workforce, are an increase in the prices of raw resources, patent infringement and other lawsuits against the company and others.

2.2.2. Internal Environment Analysis

Marketing: 4P marketing mix

First analysis that needs to be done is marketing. American Marketing Association defines marketing as activities of some institutions and a process to create, communicate, deliver and trade offers that is available to customers, clients, and partners or wide community (Kotler & Keller., 2014). Marketing activities that is labeled by McCarthy as marketing mix consist of activities about creating ideas of product, price, place, and promotion (Rufaidah.,2013).

Source:

https://www.google.com/search?q=4p+marketing&safe=active&source=lnms&tbn=isch&sa=X&ved=0ahUKEwiz86PdwYDgAhXPTn0KHZCXCVCVQQ_AUIDigB&biw=1366&bih=657#imgrc=JHffATDCpdVvYM:1. Product is something which satisfies the needs and desire of the customer. It is the actual item which is held for sale in the market.

1. **Product** is something which satisfies the needs and desire of the customer. It is the actual item which is held for sale in the market.
2. **Price** is the actual amount which the customer pays for the product.
3. **Place** includes places where the services will be performed.
4. **Promotion**, goods or service, a business has to convey the customer about the product that is going to be offered and what makes it better than the other competitor.

Company needs to know exactly what their strengths and weaknesses are because it will affect the upcoming strategy. To do this analysis, this study uses a tool called SWOT analysis. SWOT stands for Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, and Threat which is strategic factors for specific company (Wheelen and Hunger, 2012).

Strengths are the attributes, characteristics and factors give competitive advantage to the business, for instance, considerable brand value of the business, cash reserves, first mover advantage, and exclusive access to unique resources of major strengths that contribute to competitive advantage of the business.

Weakness are the attributes, characteristics and factors weaken competitiveness of the business in

the marketplace. A history of defective products, presence of huge debts and high employee turnover are examples of major weaknesses that a company may have.

According to (Reid & Bojanic, 2006), there are four concepts in formulating marketing strategy in managing new product to new market:

1. Market penetration strategy is sold to the existed market in order to increase profit.
2. Developing new product strategy is an idea to develop new product to the existing market which is mostly used in entertainment because of the rapid changes.
3. Developing new market strategy is a strategy that focuses on developing new market for product and service existed such as restaurant and hotel. They mostly use this strategy to expand the new market.
4. Diversification strategy is a product introduction strategy and new service to new market. This strategy offers long-term strategy, but it has a high risk. As a result, these implementations are required in order to get profit and give satisfaction to customers.

III- Research framework

This study is done within a company which is called PT GRAND TEXTILE INDUSTRY located in Indonesia. The study begins from the identification of the problem that the company faces. Then, the data collection is conducted in order to get the information requested by the study. The method used is SWOT analysis which is the analysis of internal and external environment of the company itself. Hence, the results and findings of six strategies to the company is presented. Finally, some strategies are recommended to the company to improve its issues throughout the organization.

It is important firstly to understand the vision and mission of PT GRANDTEX Company, secondly to analyze both the internal and external environment, and thirdly to analyze SWOT. After finishing those analysis, let's formulate the strategy that should be used with the purpose of PT GRANDTEX would start by experiencing those different types of analysis: internal environment analysis and external environment analysis.

Source: Personal investigation

IV- Methodology

This research uses qualitative research because for the part of reasons that this study is about to obtain, understand and analyze the answer of the research question. This work is focusing basically on documents from the company itself, based on observation and interview that were conducted with high responsible and some employees within the PT GRANDTEX. Thus, this study will focus more about the quality of the information that have gotten from the company and its employees.

V- Result and analysis

The following board shows the analysis of SWOT matrix.

Table 2: SWOT matrix

	<p>OPPORTUNITIES (O) (O1), Indonesia-EU CEPA (O2), TPP with United States and Japan. (O3), Constantly increasing of the population.</p>	<p>THREATS (T) (T1), Increasing of the number of competitors (T2), Consumer more and more demanding</p>
<p>STRENGTHS (S) (S1), High quality of product. (S2), Good image of the company</p>	<p>(S1, O1, O2), Market penetration</p>	<p>(S1, T1), Horizontal integration</p>
<p>WEAKNESSES (W) (W1), Quantity of product decrease. (W2), High price of raw material. (W3), Demotivation of employee (W4), Procrastination of the employee (W5), Not giving an enough consideration to NPD</p>	<p>(W2, O1, O2, O3) Backward integration (W5, O1, O2) Product development</p>	<p>Related diversification (W5, T1, T2) Market development</p>

Source: Personal investigation

For the crossing of the strengths and opportunities, this study proposes that the company will use the market penetration strategy. According to the Fred David, Strategic management, concepts and cases, 13rd edition, p.137, a company can use the market penetration when current markets are not saturated with a particular product or service, when the usage rate of present customers could be increased significantly, when increased economies of scale provide major competitive advantages. Here the company has many opportunities to be taken in order to increase their sale and also the

constantly increasing of the population insure the existence of consumer. The company is known as a high-quality provider and also has a good image so challenging to enter to the market is possible by improving the marketing effort. Such as applying public relations by doing some event sponsorship, employee relations. This will be done in order to maximize the strengths of the company and get more profit by acquiring the opportunities.

For the crossing of the strengths and threats, this study proposes that the company will use the horizontal integration strategy. According to the Fred David, Strategic management, concepts and cases, 13rd edition, p.137, the company can use it when an organization can gain monopolistic characteristics in a particular area or region without being challenged by the federal government for “tending substantially” to reduce competition, when an organization competes in a growing industry, when increased economies of scale provide major competitive advantages, when an organization has both the capital and human talent needed to successfully manage an expanded organization. And here the company has already a good image and also their product is satisfying the consumer but their threats the competitor who are increasing so for contouring it they can they can use the horizontal integration strategy because it will allow them to gain more control over the firm’s competitors.

For the crossing of the weaknesses and opportunities, this study proposes that the company use the backward integration strategy. According to the Fred David, Strategic management, concepts and cases, 13rd edition, p.137. The company can use it when the price of the suppliers is too much expensive. The price of the raw materials is among the company problem so for solving that the company can apply this strategy. By changing a supplier for the raw materials. The company can also use the product development because among the company problem is NPD so if they arrive to solve this problem, they can get a place of leader. They can use the product development because this strategy will push the company to develop their product and will allow them to get a new market share.

For the crossing of the weaknesses and threats, this study proposes that the company will use the related diversification. According to the Fred David, Strategic management, concepts and cases, 13rd edition, p.137, a company can use the related diversification strategy when adding new, but related, products would significantly enhance the sales of current products, when new, but related, products could be offered at highly competitive prices. So, in order to fight against the threats and

also to minimize the weaknesses this strategy can allows the company to stay on the market. The company can also use the market development strategy. A company can use this strategy when an organization is very successful at what it does, when new unsaturated markets exist, when an organization has the needed capital and human resources to manage expanded operations. The situation of the company, they can use this strategy in order to help the company to acquire the opportunities which present to them. It will be also used to minimize the impacts of the threats on their activities.

VI- Discussion and conclusion

The study of “SWOT analysis at PT GRAND TEXTILE INDUSTRY in Indonesia” showed that the problem of production is not only due to the problem of machine but also due to some others problems. That’s why during this study, the internal analysis of the company was considered to know all factors; and the influence of its external environment. The study showed that knowing the external environment are as important as knowing the internal environment with the intention of from those analysis, we have gotten some appropriate strategies which can be used to help the company to reach its goal, develop and ensure its sustainability. Those strategies are market penetration, market development, horizontal integration, backward integration, product development and related diversification.

In order to help the company PT GRAND TEXTILE to reduce its production problem and also to allow the company to ensure its sustainability, this study proposes these following strategies:

1. Backward integration strategy. This strategy is used when the company has a problem with the supplier such as a too costly supplier. Due to the high price of the raw material is among one of the causes of the decreasing of production, this study proposes to PT GRANDTEX to decrease the quantity of product bought from its current supplier and find another supplier which offer a more affordable price. So, it would only buy the most important raw material that it needs from one supplier and buy the others raw materials from another supplier.
2. Product development strategy. This strategy is used when the company competes on a market where the major competitors offer better-quality products at comparable prices, when an organization competes in a high-growth industry, when an organization has especially strong research and development capabilities. PT GRANDTEX has a good NPD department and an experienced employee, so let’s propose by giving an important consideration to the NPD where it

would bring the company to a better place on the market. With NPD highly considerate would lead the company to a higher competitive advantage and a better position on the market.

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RAKOTOARISOA ZAMELINA ARNOLD

Strategic Management in Master Management Program

Former graduate student at PARAHYANGAN CATHOLIC UNIVERSITY,

Bandung INDONESIA

arnoldzam88@gmail.com

+261343095446

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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